

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

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VARIABLE SPEED CONTROLLED BY EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF WIND TURBINE WITH FAULT MONITORING: A DESIGN AND PREDICTIVE LEARNING APPROACH

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Abstract

Wind turbines are designed using the suction power of the compressor attached to the turbine blades. Components of wind turbines undergoes various state changes including transformations from normal state to blocked state or defect state. Condition based algorithms and maintenance tools are made used for monitoring these recurrent faults. In this research, classification algorithms are employed to construct the prediction models for wind turbine faults. Prediction of fault is done in three stages. It is followed by 1) prediction of a fault by mechanical component degradation 2) prediction of a fault by pitch faults 3) identification of unseen faults. A comparative analysis of various data mining algorithms are reported based on the data collected at a large wind farm. Support Vector Machine models provided the best accuracy among all algorithms tested. The robustness of the predictive model is validated for faults that have occurred at turbines with previously unseen data.

Key words: Data mining, Wind Turbine Component analysis, Fuzzy clustering algorithm.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wind turbines are having breakdown in its working due to many reasons. The total downtime is divided into categories according to causes of downtime (Table 1): failure (60 %), minor disturbance with no repairs needed (29 %), icing (4 %), main In the current trends of wind energy renewable sources, the generation of energy power form the wind turbines are statistically measured tenancy (4 %) and network disturbance (2 %). Failure statistics is made from the major disturbances. Downtime due to failures is divided into component subcategories indicating the count and share of downtime for each component. The distribution of the numbers of failures is also shown in Figure 5. From these diagrams one can see that gear failures (19 %) have caused the most downtime, closely followed by failures in the hydraulic system (15%). Failures in the hydraulic system make up the greatest part of the total number of failures (20 %). The actual values for each component can be seen in Table 1.

Wind Power is the world's fastest growing renewable energy source. With the developing and growing of wind power, reducing the cost of generating the wind energy becomes a critical issue. The research results discussed in this paper have been derived from data collected at 17 wind turbines. IND destined energy to grow is regarded in importance as a major in the renewable decades to resource come. The expansion of wind farms makes their operations and maintenance (O&M) an important issue. It is not unusual for the maintenance/repair cost of wind turbine components to exceed their procurement cost [1], [2]. According to the data presented in [3], maintenance cost alone may account for at least 10% of the total generation cost. To address O&M issues, traditional maintenance practices such as periodic and corrective maintenance are being replaced with condition-based monitoring and maintenance.

State-of-the-art condition maintenance applications in the wind industry are discussed in [4]. Condition-based monitoring approaches continuously monitor the performance of wind turbine components with installed sensors and equipment. Vibration analysis [8], optical strain measurements [9], and oil particle analysis [10] are commonly used in condition monitoring. Performance monitoring is another promising approach that closely resembles condition monitoring. It utilizes parameters such as gearbox oil temperature, and tower acceleration. Performance monitoring is a cost-effective approach to analyze wind turbine performance as the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system records various wind turbine parameters that could be fault informative.

Data mining has been used as a viable approach to performance monitoring of wind turbines. Related data-mining algorithm applications include fault diagnosis [1], [11], modeling of abnormal behavior [12], [13], and power curve monitoring [14]. Other related research includes identification of status patterns of wind turbines [15], in which the authors employed association rule mining to identify patterns within the individual statuses. Here the term status represents a potential fault. In reference [16], the authors employed an adaptive control strategy to gain maximum power and minimum torque ramp.

Considering the role of converters in optimizing wind turbine performance, a stream of research has focused on reliability assessment of wind turbines [17], [18].

The research reported in this paper utilized data-mining algorithms to predict wind turbine states. The results presented in the paper are based on the analysis of data obtained from 17 wind turbines (1.5 MW) of a large wind farm in Blairsburg, Iowa and some of the wind farms in India. The values of parameters recorded at 10-s intervals (10-s data) over a four-month period constitute the dataset for this research.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II describes wind turbine states along with a discussion of the data preprocessing. Section III provides the computational results. Section IV concludes the research and presents future research directions.

II. SURVEY

Speed variation in the wind turbine blades and the rotor are considered as an important criteria for wind based electricity generation. Various methods and hardware/software configurations were adopted newly by many research works carried out in the past 14 years in the field of power system. In this research work, a new hardware additional component is configured so that the wind speed can be maintained at a constant rate of 10m/s or 1440rpm. The speed of the rotor blades are frequently monitored using a sensor component.

Many wind energy system have been developed to achieve some degree of speed variation consistency: (1) dual-speed generators with pole switching (the use of a lower speed in low wind conditions improves performance and reduces noise emissions); (2) variable-resistance asynchronous generators for a low range of variable speed; (3) doubly fed induction generators (DFIGs) for a moderate range of variable speed; and finally, (4) direct-drive multi pole synchronous generator systems and (5) hybrid systems (combination of multi pole generators with small gearboxes), both for a wide range of variable speed.

Especially dominant in new markets is the DFIG, also called the wound rotor induction generator. In this machine, the stator windings are directly connected to the grid, while a frequency converter interfaces between the standard wound rotor and the grid. The stator winding connection carries most of the power production, although the frequency converter may carry up to a third of the total power, depending on the operating mode. This configuration allows the machine to control the slip in the generator, and thus the rotor speed can vary moderately, achieving better aerodynamic efficiency. Furthermore, as the converter controls the rotor voltage magnitude and phase angle, partial control of active and reactive power is also possible.

The proposed system is the DFIG generator controlled wind turbine connected to the compressor cylinder, with an anemometer to detect the wind circulation with its speed and quantity of air. A relay is used to push the filled in air of the cylinder connected to the compressor in wind blades to drive the rotor in a constant speed, which, in further, can improve the aerodynamic efficiency. Hardware configuration is alone enhanced to maintain the rotor speed as constant.

In section II, prediction models are developed for monitoring fault and non fault state in wind turbine and in section III, models for improving the power generation and aerodynamic efficiency is discussed.

III. MODELS FOR FAULT MONITORING IN WIND TURBINE STATES

The framework for building prediction models is provided in Fig. 1. An abstraction of turbine states is used to categorize the output data into a number of states using expert knowledge. Model building involves using various data-mining algorithms. The models are then tested. The generated dataset is used to construct models for Phase-I and Phase-II predictions. The fault states are derived from the survey on a large wind farm at Finland [3] and they listed in the Table 1.

Identified States
Fault
Turbine OK
Weather downtime
Maintenance downtime

Fig.3.

Table 1. Wind turbine states collected by SCADA system sampled at a frequency of 0.1Hz.

In order to develop a prediction model for predicting the turbine states, the data collected by the SCADA system is sampled at the frequency of 0.1Hz. These state information derived from a survey paper, states that variable rotor speed control can lead to an efficient wind power generation. The wind turbine fault state occurrence can be reduced by controlling the variable speed of the rotor blades. This can be achieved using the conceptual model stated in Fig.3.

IV. MODELS FOR EFFICIENT DESIGN OF WIND TURBINE

The basic component architecture of the wind turbine and its blades is shown in the Fig.1, which consists of Anemometer used to sense the air in and around the wind turbine. About 10m of air detection can be achieved by this device. This device is also used in the proposed system to monitor the compressor cylinder pitch used for storing the air by suction process. When the cylinder is filled by air, a relay is used to push the air into the rotor generator relay. The hardware components added in enhancement to the basic wind turbine architecture is the two relays and sensor circuits.

Fig.1 Basic Component architecture of wind turbines

III. MODELS FOR FAULT MONITORING IN WIND TURBINE SPEED

The variable speed monitoring in wind farms can be achieved by a generic qualitative power curve for a variable-speed pitch-controlled wind turbine, shown in Fig. 2. Four zones and two areas are indicated in the figure [12]. The rated power P_r of the wind turbine (that is, the actual power supplied to the grid at wind speed greater than V_r) separates the graph into two main areas. Below rated power, the wind turbine produces only a fraction of its total design power, and therefore an optimization control strategy needs to be performed. Conversely, above rated power, a limitation control strategy is required.

Fig.2 Power Curve of a wind turbine and control zones

Fig.3 Conceptual model

III. REQUIREMENTS

Parameter Selection: A Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system records more than 100 wind turbine parameters that can be broadly categorized into: 1) wind turbine performance parameters, 2) wind turbine control parameters, and 3) wind turbine non controllable parameters. Parameters such as power, generator speed, and rotor speed are the performance parameters, whereas, blade pitch angle and generator torque are controllable parameters. Wind speed is the only non- controllable parameter. In the research reported in this paper, a combination of turbine performance parameters, control parameters, and non-controllable parameters are used to predict the wind turbine states. To minimize the data dimensionality and to remove irrelevant parameters, parameter selection algorithms are used. A month of data was used for parameter selection and algorithm learning

. A stratified subset of the original data was used for parameter selection to make the process computationally efficient. Fig. 3 displays the original and stratified data. Distribution of the output

class is preserved in stratified data to avoid bias towards any specific class. Three different data-mining algorithms, wrapper with genetic search (WGS) [9], [10], wrapper with best first search (WBFS) [11], and boosting tree algorithm (BTA) [12] were selected to determine relevant parameters for prediction of turbine states. Wrapper is a supervised learning approach using different search techniques to select the relevant parameters by performing ten-fold cross validation.

The problem of over fitting due to 10 Cross Fold Validation is also removed using the random split of training and testing data set by holding out 40% of training data for testing. One round of cross-validation involves partitioning a sample of data into complementary subsets, performing the analysis on one subset (called the training set), and validating the analysis on the other subset (called the validation set or testing set). To reduce variability, multiple rounds of cross-validation are performed using different partitions, and the validation results are averaged over the rounds.

V SUPPORT VECTOR MODELING Vs RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM

On analyzing the support vector models for the fault conditions identified in a wind energy conversion system, the following statistics of fault conditions are recurrent. The training data set are set to ten- fold cross validation and shows that auto random forest algorithms have better accuracy than SVM models in case of fault state identification. All six predictors were considered for each split. The full series has four hundred trees. The minimum error with the training data occurs with 393 trees. The minimum error with the test data occurs with 289 trees. The minimum point is smoothed by 5 trees. The specified minimum number of trees is 10. The tree series will be pruned to 289 trees. Maximum depth of any tree in the series = 5. Average number of group splits in each tree = 31.4.

Fig.4 Trees generated by Random Forest Algorithm

Among 400 trees generated by the Random Forest algorithm, one of the trees is shown in the Fig. 4, which depicts the weight of each and every state identified in the WECS assigned by the neural networks. The classification rate and the misclassification rate are computed for each and every node.

Target category of Fault State = Fault by SVM

Total records = 170
Accuracy = 67.22%
Precision =67.35%
Recall = 99.69%
F-Measure =0.8057

Table 2. Fault State classification under SVM models

The classification parameters of the target category identified is recorded for each and every target class including weather downtime and maintenance downtime. Number of True positives and false positives and the rate of classification for the target class “Fault State” is specified in the Table 2.

Fig.5 SVM model

The SVM models for the fault state category is computed and predicted with 67.22% of accuracy, whereas the recall measure is highly accurate to find the fault class of the wind turbine states.

By using the Neural Network algorithm, weights of each and every fault state is assigned to the class labels. Then random forest learning algorithm is applied to the training data set which in turn is achieved with 62.22% accuracy in finding the fault state.

Target category of Fault State = Fault by Random Forest

When ten- fold cross validation is applied to the training data, Random forest algorithm has shown an accuracy of 65.56%.

Total records = 170
Accuracy = 65.56%
Precision =65.70%
Recall = 98.54%
F-Measure = 1.0524

Table 3. Fault State classification under Random Forest Algorithm

VI EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The SVM model generated for the classification of fault states in a wind energy conversion system has identified the fault class with the accuracy of 97 percent whereas the Tree Boost algorithm in contrast has identified the true positive cases and the fault classes at an accuracy rate of 97.5 percent with 400 trees. It shows that Tree Boost algorithm is suitably better than Support vector models for classifying the fault state in WECS. The neural network model is used to assign the weight of every fault state identified in the WECS.

The ROC curve achieved in the case of SVM learning method show that when recall value of the miner increases, the precision of the corresponding miner also increases, thereby increasing the accuracy.

Figure 1.Recall/precision curve of the search with and without personalization

Figure 1 shows the performance of the ranked search results returned in step 4, compared to the results obtained without personalization. The poor precision of the search without personalization at the lowest recall levels is due to the fact that the image-based retrieval algorithm returns initially

irrelevant results. Overall experiments show that the proposed ontology-based personalization is particularly helpful in difficult multimedia retrieval tasks.

VII CONCLUSION

Even though high accuracy is obtained in the case random forest algorithm, the number of wind turbine fault states and false positive case mentioning the misclassification rate is identified largely by SVM models rather than Tree Boost models. Hence I conclude that SVM models are better than Tree Boost algorithms in identifying the misclassification rate and fault classification rate. When ten cross fold validation is used the tree boost algorithms can be improved further. Previously, Tree boost algorithm was not achieved with this accuracy of 97.57 % of accuracy.

After the process of optimizing the algorithm with ten cross fold validation, Tree boost algorithm is improved with its accuracy rate. Whereas the SVM miner with 67.22% of accuracy is enough with the recall rate of 99.69% to detect the fault class of the wind turbine accurately.

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